

A Review on Pharmacovigilance in the Treatment of Diabetic Patients

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ABSTRACT

The pharmacovigilance is essential in the assurance of safety and reliability of the treatment and antidiabetic drugs. The review gives a summary of the findings of the recent articles on adverse drug reaction (ADRs) which are reported in the patients of diabetes (type 1 and type 2). The safety profiles of various categories of drugs including GLP-1 receptor agonists, SGLT2 inhibitors and insulin therapeutics are analyzed. In addition to that, the review provides the significance of pharmacovigilance databases in identifying and preventing ADRs, particularly in the very vulnerable populations, namely the old people. The way the machine learning algorithm can forecast ADRs and how this could assist in enhancing drug safety monitoring is also described. It was reviewed that the most frequently reported events in the patients despite the given differences are ADRs, such as hypoglycemia, gastrointestinal intolerance, and genitourinary infections. In addition, early notification and identification are very useful in amplifying the patient outcomes and reporting the safer clinical practice. Through the comprehensive analysis, the necessity of the continuous pharmacovigilance is revealed in order to optimize diabetes management and patient outcome.

Keywords: Pharmacovigilance, Diabetes Mellitus, Adverse Drug Reactions, SGLT2 Inhibitors, Digital Pharmacovigilance.

INTRODUCTION

T2DM is a chronic metabolic syndrome, which is insulin-resistant and insulin-deficient, resulting in hyperglycemia¹. T2DM has been gradually gaining prevalence in the world, posing major threats to the population health². The newer antidiabetic agents have offered more treatment methods to help a clinician to manage this condition³. They are sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 inhibitors (SGLT2 inhibitors), glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist (GLP-1 RAs), and dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor (DPP-4 inhibitors), which do not only enhance glycemic regulation but also have cardiovascular and renal effects^{4,5}.

The action mechanism of SGLT2 inhibitors like empagliflozin, dapagliflozin, and canagliflozin is the inhibition of glucose reabsorption in the proximal renal tubules, which causes the excretion of urinary glucose and prevent the worsening of glucose levels in the blood⁶. These agents have also proved to be

useful in lowering cardiovascular events as well as renal disease progression in T2DM patients. Regardless of their therapeutic benefits, safety issues remain, and this requires strict pharmacovigilance⁷. Such adverse drug reactions (ADRs) as genital infections and ketoacidosis may negatively impact adherence and outcomes of SGLT2 inhibitors. The pharmacovigilance plays a very vital role in observing such events and putting the right measures of risk control into place⁸.

GLP-1 receptor agonists which include liraglutide, semaglutide and dulaglutide are replicas of endogenous GLP-1, which will boost insulin secretion in a glucose-dependent way and reduce glucagon secretions. They are effective agents to enhance glycemic control, weight loss reduction and cardiovascular protection⁹. But according to pharmacovigilance research, there was gastrointestinal intolerance and rare ADRs such as pancreatitis, which accentuates the necessity of continued monitoring^{10,11}. These effects have been

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confirmed in real-world data and have found new safety signals, which were examined as to their long-term safety.

DPP-4 inhibitors are shown to inhibit the enzyme dipeptidyl peptidase-4, such as sitagliptin, saxagliptin and linagliptin which prolong the action of incretin, and increase insulin secretion. They have most often good tolerance with a positive safety record¹². The pharmacovigilance information, though, identifies rare but serious ADRs, which highlights the relevance of the continued post-marketing surveillance¹³.

Pharmacovigilance is tenacious in the identification and prevention of ADRs of newer antidiabetic agents. The constant interaction of medical staff, regulators, and patients is needed in order to achieve drug safety and maximize therapeutic effects. The objective of the review is to give a thorough analysis of ADRs involving SGLT 2 inhibitors, GLP 1 receptor agonists and DPP 4 inhibitors in the last ten years. The paper to define common and rare ADRs, analyze its clinical implications, and explain the relevance of pharmacovigilance systems to better clinical management of diabetes by synthesizing results of pharmacovigilance databases, clinical trials and real-world studies.

Figure 1. Pathophysiology and drug classes in Diabetes mellitus

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 STUDY DESIGN

The current paper has a narrative review design, which incorporates peer-reviewed literature on pharmacovigilance, diabetes management, and adverse drug reactions (ADRs). The research process followed the Preferred Reporting Items of systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) guidelines in terms of systematic literature choice and a report²³. It was aimed at examining trends, gaps and developments in pharmacovigilance systems in both

global and Indian approaches in relation to diabetes therapy.

The data sources and strategy of search were presented using the subsequent section:

3.2 DATA SOURCES AND SEARCH STRATEGY

An extensive search was performed by searching databases which included PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus, Web of Science and Google Scholar to locate articles in English language with the period specified as January 2010 to May 2025. Keywords that were

used in search included free-text terms such as pharmacovigilance, adverse drug reactions, diabetes mellitus, antidiabetic drugs, drug safety, reporting system and post-marketing surveillance using Medical Subject headings (MeSH). Results were narrowed using the Boolean operators (AND/OR). Additional studies were also screened on reference lists of key articles²⁴.

3.3 INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Inclusion

criteria:

Peer-reviewed original research, reviews, and meta-analyses focusing on pharmacovigilance in diabetes management; studies describing ADRs associated with antidiabetic drugs; English-language articles published between 2010–2025; and reports from WHO, Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, and other regulatory agencies related to diabetes drug safety.

Exclusion

criteria:

Non-peer-reviewed sources, editorials, or conference abstracts without full text; studies not related to diabetes or pharmacovigilance; and articles lacking methodological transparency or statistical validation.

3.4 DATA EXTRACTION AND MANAGEMENT

All selected studies were evaluated independently by two reviewers. Data extraction focused on the type of antidiabetic drug investigated, study design, population characteristics, nature and frequency of ADRs, pharmacovigilance tools used, and key findings²⁵. Changes were achieved by discussing and coming to consensus. The extracted data were inputted in Microsoft Excel 365 that was coded and thematically grouped.

3.5 QUALITY ASSESSMENT

The quality of the included studies in terms of methodology was measured with the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Critical Appraisal Checklist of observational and review studies²⁶. The studies were rated on the level of clarity of objectives, validity of data sources, ADR classification and strength of

evidence. Narrative synthesis was only applied to medium and high-quality studies.

3.6 DATA SYNTHESIS

Information obtained was synthesized in five broad areas, namely, global pharmacovigilance framework, antidiabetic agent ADR patterns, national pharmacovigilance activity, digital developments, and policy issues. The synthesis focused on the determination of gaps in the existing literature and suggestions in the context of enhancing pharmacovigilance through the time-to-onset aspect of antidiabetic drugs, which enhances the fidelity of the pharmacovigilance measures²⁰.

Figure 2. Methodology flowchart for narrative review on pharmacovigilance in diabetes management.

4. GLOBAL PHARMACOVIGILANCE FRAMEWORK IN DIABETES

Pharmacovigilance (PV) is an important approach in public health, which is designed to identify, evaluate, comprehend and avoid adverse drug reactions (ADRs), safe the task of using medicines, and maximize therapeutic achievements. This is particularly relevant in chronic disease problems such as diabetes mellitus where long term pharmacotherapy and polypharmacy elevate the chances of developing drug related problems.

4.1 WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION (WHO) PROGRAMS

Global pharmacovigilance has its basis in the WHO Programme for International Drug Monitoring (PIDM) that was developed in 1968²⁸. The program is coordinated by the Uppsala Monitoring Centre (UMC) in Sweden; it compiles ADR reports within the countries and aids in sending an early alert on drug safety signals²⁷. The common antidiabetic medications, such as metformin, sulfonylureas, and insulin are commonly monitored because of their prevalence and possible appearance of such serious ADRs as hypoglycemia, lactic acidosis, and cardiovascular issues²⁹.

4.2 INTERNATIONAL REPORTING SYSTEMS

The ADR reporting and analysis is standardized in a few international databases:

- **VigiBase:** WHO VigiBase is a global ICSR data base that includes millions of ADR reports including ones involving antidiabetic agents and is able to identify signals and safety review³⁰.
- **EudraVigilance:** This system is operated by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and it is used in the monitoring ADRs of diabetic medications across the EU countries and it is also used in the identification of safety concerns of diabetic medicines in an opportune manner³¹.
- **FDA Adverse Event Reporting System (FAERS):** In the U.S., ADR data is collected through the FDA by clinical practice, post-marketing clinical studies as well as patient

submissions with emphasis on antidiabetic drugs used frequently³².

4.3 PHARMACOVIGILANCE NATIONAL INITIATIVES

The National The PV programs work hand-in-hand with the global activities by supporting the region-related ADR monitoring requirements:

India: There is a project that was started in 2010 as the Pharmacovigilance Programme of India (PvPI) which involves ADR reporting throughout India, with a special undertaking on high-risk drugs such as antidiabetic agents³³. Preclinical trials according to PvPI point to frequent ADRs, including hypoglycemia, gastrointestinal upsets, and hepatotoxicity³⁴.

United States and Europe: Risk assessment and mitigation strategy (REMS) is enforced by national bodies to track high-risk diabetic drugs, such as SGLT-2 inhibitors and GLP-1 receptor agonists⁵⁰.

4.4 INTERNATIONAL PHARMACOVIGILANCE PROBLEMS

Although PV systems have improved nowadays, there are several issues:

1. The underreporting of ADRs remains a perennial hindrance to the implementation of PV program where 60-90 percent of ADRs are usually not reported especially in developing states³⁵.
2. Lack of data heterogeneity Data heterogeneity occurs due to the variations in the format of reporting, ADR classification, and terminologies across countries⁵¹.
3. The lack of real-time monitoring and predictive analytics is caused by the limited integration of digital tools in the majority of national systems³⁶.
4. Awakenings about awareness and training of the professionals involved in healthcare hinder the accurate and consistent reporting of ADR.

These problems can be dealt with by harmonizing reporting standards, digital pharmacovigilance and capacity building; which are essential towards

enhancing the use of medication in diabetic patients worldwide³⁷.

Organization / Database	Region / Country	Function	Relevance to Diabetes Therapy	Key Feature / Data Volume	Reference
VigiBase (WHO-UMC)	Global (≥150 countries)	Centralized ADR collection	Collects ADRs for metformin, insulin, SGLT2i, etc.	>35 million ADR cases	30
EudraVigilance (EMA)	Europe	EU drug safety monitoring	Monitors GLP-1 RAs, SGLT2i safety updates	>15 million ADR reports	31
FAERS (FDA)	USA	Post-marketing safety	High focus on DKA, pancreatitis in diabetes drugs	>20 million ADRs	32
PvPI (India)	India	National ADR database	Focus on hypoglycemia and GI intolerance	600+ ADR monitoring centers	33,34
Health Canada Vigilance	Canada	National ADR program	Insulin and metformin ADR patterns	~1 million ADR reports	—

5. PATTERNS OF ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS IN DIABETIC THERAPY

Diabetes mellitus is treated using a variety of classes of pharmacological therapies, which comprise insulin, biguanides, sulfonylureas, thiazolidinedione, DPP-4, GLP-1 receptor agonists, and SGLT-2 agonists. Although these medications are useful in blood glucose regulation, they have multiple adverse drug reactions (ADRs) that may affect patient safety, adherence, and treatment results²⁹. The age-associated physiological alterations, polypharmacy, and comorbidities increase the susceptibility of elderly diabetic patients to adverse drug reactions, and focused pharmacovigilance is essential in this population¹⁷. An anticancer drug study presented findings of Alpelisib, which can cause diabetic ketoacidosis and therefore highlights the need to keep close track of individuals with diabetic patients experiencing acute incidences of metabolic dehydration¹⁴. Active monitoring of glycemic variability when using pharmacotherapy has been supported by the pharmacovigilance signal analyses as one of the serious safety concerns when taking drugs, highlighting drug-induced hyperglycemia and secondary diabetes¹⁸.

5.1 INSULIN

Insulin therapy remains the cornerstone of treatment for type 1 diabetes and advanced type 2 diabetes. Common ADRs include:

- Hypoglycemia: The most frequent and potentially life-threatening complication³⁸.
- Weight gain: Due to anabolic effects of insulin.
- Injection site reactions: Pain, erythema, or lipodystrophy.

5.2 BIGUANIDES(METFORMIN)

Metformin is the first-line therapy for type 2 diabetes due to its efficacy and cardiovascular safety profile. ADRs associated with metformin include:

- Gastrointestinal disturbances: Nausea, diarrhea, and abdominal discomfort (15–25% of patients)³⁹.
- Lactic acidosis: Rare but serious, particularly in patients with renal impairment.
- Vitamin B12 deficiency: Chronic use may reduce B12 absorption.

5.3 SULFONYLUREAS

Sulfonylureas stimulate insulin secretion and are widely prescribed. ADRs include:

- Hypoglycemia: Especially in elderly patients or those with renal impairment⁴⁰.
- Weight gain.
- Dermatological reactions: Rash, photosensitivity.

5.4 THIAZOLIDINEDIONES (TZDs)

TZDs such as pioglitazone and rosiglitazone improve insulin sensitivity. ADRs include:

- Fluid retention and edema: Leading to potential heart failure exacerbation⁴¹.
- Weight gain.
- Hepatotoxicity: Rare, requires liver function monitoring.

5.5 DPP-4 INHIBITORS

Dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitors are generally well tolerated. ADRs include:

- Mild gastrointestinal symptoms⁴².
- Rare hypersensitivity reactions.
- Risk of pancreatitis: Controversial, but reported in post-marketing surveillance⁴³

5.6 GLP-1 RECEPTOR AGONISTS

These injectable agents provide glucose-dependent insulin secretion enhancement. ADRs include:

- Gastrointestinal intolerance: Nausea, vomiting, diarrhea⁴⁴.
- Injection site reactions.
- Pancreatitis risk: Rare but observed in some pharmacovigilance reports⁴⁵.
- Recent real-world pharmacovigilance studies report that Tirzepatide demonstrates an overall favorable safety profile; however, continuous monitoring is necessary to identify rare or long-term adverse events¹⁶.

5.7 SGLT-2 INHIBITORS

Sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitors reduce glucose reabsorption in the kidneys. ADRs include:

- Genital mycotic infections: Most common ADR⁴⁶.
- Volume depletion and hypotension⁴⁷.
- Rare diabetic ketoacidosis (euglycemic DKA)⁴⁸.

Post-marketing data reveal that Ertugliflozin is associated with elevated signals of metabolic (e.g., ketoacidosis), infectious (genital/urinary tract), and renal adverse events, stressing the need for heightened pharmacovigilance in routine diabetes care¹⁹. Pharmacovigilance data on Teplizumab reveal immune-related adverse events, highlighting the need for close monitoring of new diabetes immunotherapies²².

6. SUMMARY TABLE OF ADRs BY DRUG CLASS

Drug Class	Common ADRs	Frequency	Severity	Reference
Insulin	Hypoglycemia, weight gain, injection site reactions	High	Moderate–Severe	38
Metformin	GI disturbances, lactic acidosis, B12 deficiency	Moderate	Mild–Severe	39
Sulfonylureas	Hypoglycemia, weight gain, rash	High	Moderate	40
Thiazolidinediones	Edema, weight gain, hepatotoxicity	Moderate	Moderate–Severe	41
DPP-4 inhibitors	GI upset, hypersensitivity, pancreatitis	Low	Mild–Moderate	42,43

GLP-1 agonists	GI intolerance, injection reactions, pancreatitis	Moderate	Mild–Severe	44,45
SGLT-2 inhibitors	Genital infections, hypotension, ketoacidosis	Moderate	Mild–Severe	46,48

7. PHARMACOVIGILANCE PROGRAMS AND REGULATIONS

The effective decision-making of pharmacovigilance (PV) depends on well-developed programs and regulatory systems, so that the possible adverse drug reactions (ADRs) of patients having chronic diseases like diabetes mellitus may be detected, reported and prevented early²⁷. The international, regional, and local systems of the pharmacovigilance work are mostly based on the post-marketing surveillance as the adverse effect that was not discovered during the clinical trials is revealed, assessed, and controlled when medicines are used in practice in the real world²¹. International Pharmacovigilance Programs are conducted in accordance with international requirements⁵¹.

7.1 INTERNATIONAL PHARMACOVIGILANCE PROGRAMS

International Pharmacovigilance Programs are conducted in compliance with international requirements. The global PV activities are based on the World Health Organization (WHO) Programme for International Drug Monitoring (PIDM), which is coordinated by Uppsala Monitoring Centre (UMC). PIDM receives Individual Case Safety Reports (ICSRs) in more than 150 member countries and has VigiBase, a central global ADR monitoring database³⁰. The system is essential to monitoring ADRs in common antidiabetic drugs, which are metformin, insulin, sulfonylureas, and newer drugs such as SGLT-2 inhibitors²⁹.

The other major international programs are:

- EudraVigilance (European Union): It manages the ADRs in EU member states and assists the regulatory measures of updating the labels, warning against safety risks, and restricting the use of high-risk antidiabetic medications³².

- FDA Adverse Event Reporting System (FAERS, USA): FAERS receives post-marketing data of ADRs in healthcare providers, manufacturers, and patients to present safety signals particularly in drugs with high hypoglycemia or cardiovascular safety risk³².

To supplement the international frameworks and meet the challenges in the region on safety issues, the national PV programs execute the policies of regulations:

7.2.1 INDIA

In 2010, the Pharmacovigilance Programme of India (PvPI), established by the Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, observes ADRs in the country, including those with antidiabetic therapy³³. PvPI has put in place a network of Adverse Drug Reaction Monitoring centres (AMCs) in the hospitals and health clinics whereby reports are collected systematically and analyzed. The operations of PvPI have resulted in more recognition among the medical workers and higher rates of reporting³⁴.

7.2.2 UNITED STATES

FDA imposes Risk Evaluation and Mitigation Strategies (REMS) on high risk diabetic drugs, namely, SGLT-2 inhibitors and GLP-1 receptor agonists. REMS programs entail compulsory provider education, patient surveillance and post-marketing surveillance to counter extreme cases of ADRs like ketoacidosis, pancreatitis, and heart attacks⁴⁹.

7.2.3 EUROPE

Under the EMA regulations, pharmaceutical companies are expected to file Periodic Safety Update Reports (PSURs) as well as have a solid pharmacovigilance system in place concerning drugs that are already in the market. The European PV models also focus on patient-based reporting,

automatic filing of ICSRs, and integration of the hospital information systems to detect real-time ADs.

7.3 EMERGING DIGITAL PHARMACOVIGILANCE SYSTEMS

The current pharmacovigilance activities can be altered as part of the worldwide digital health technology integration, artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and big data analytics³⁶. Artificial intelligence-powered platforms are able to anticipate ADR risk, identify safety indicators more early and process high volumes of data in electronic health records and social media and pharmacy-vigilance databases. Such systems are specifically applicable in diabetes management where the complexity of ADR monitoring is caused by polypharmacy and comorbidities.

7.4 PROBLEMS AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

There are a number of challenges that despite structured PV programs exist:

- Lack of full ADR data and under reporting of PV systems limit the effectiveness of PV systems³⁵.
- Electronic ADR reporting and patient monitoring can not be established because of resource limitations in developing nations.
- The standardization of the ADR terminology and the connection to the different systems worldwide is still a key to the successful sharing of data.

To solve these issues, international PV frameworks are changing to encompass digital surveillance, engagement with the patients, and interoperable reporting. Enforcement of regulatory policies, increase in healthcare professional training and the use of predictive analytics are key to enhancing drug safety among diabetic patients⁵².

Figure 3. Regulatory Flow of ADR Detection and Reporting

8. FUTURE PROSPECTS AND DIGITAL PHARMACOVIGILANCE

Pharmacovigilance is a rapidly evolving area because of the technological development, big data analytics, and patient-centered care models. At this level, such innovations can play a significant role in enhancing the early detection, prediction and prevention of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) particularly in chronic conditions like diabetes mellitus, where polypharmacy and prolonged exposure to drugs predisposes patients to medication-related complications³⁶.

8.1 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING

Pharmacovigilance is being enhanced through the use of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), and algorithms are being incorporated into pharmacovigilance to improve signal detection and risk prediction. Machine learning methods have demonstrated significant potential to predict the adverse drug reactions, increase the accuracy and responsiveness of pharmacovigilance procedures¹⁵. The use of AI systems can help to analyze big data of electronic health records, spontaneous reporting databases, and social media to determine possible ADRs earlier than what conventional approaches would do³⁷. These tools allow:

- Predictive modelling to predict patient-specific ADR risks depending on demographics, comorbidities and polypharmacy.
- Unstructured clinical notes and post-marketing data signal detection Automated identification of signals in unstructured clinical data.
- Neuromorphic clinical decision support to optimize drug use and dosing⁵³.

8.2 DIGITAL HEALTH MONITORING

The application of digital health technologies, such as wearables, smartphone applications, and remote monitoring devices, is being considered more and more to monitor glycemic, cardiovascular, and other vital signs in real-time⁵⁴. Implementation of these platforms into pharmacovigilance structures makes it possible.

- Continuous monitoring of drug efficacy and safety.
- Early identification of adverse events, such as hypoglycemia or hypotension with antidiabetic drugs.
- Patient engagement and self-reporting of ADRs, improving overall reporting rates⁵⁵.

8.3 BIG DATA AND REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE

The utilization of big data and real-world evidence (RWE) from claims databases, electronic health records, and population registries enhances pharmacovigilance research⁶⁰. RWE provides insights into:

- Rare or long-term ADRs that may not be captured in clinical trials.
- Comparative safety profiles of multiple antidiabetic therapies in diverse populations.
- Risk stratification for high-risk patient subgroups, supporting personalized medicine approaches⁵⁶.

8.4 BLOCKCHAIN AND DATA SECURITY IN PHARMACOVIGILANCE

Blockchain technology is emerging as a secure, transparent platform for ADR reporting and data sharing⁵⁷. Its key advantages include:

- Ensuring integrity and traceability of ADR reports.
- Facilitating interoperability between national and international pharmacovigilance systems.
- Reducing data manipulation or loss, thereby improving confidence in PV decision-making⁵⁸.

8.5 PATIENT CENTERED PHARMACOVIGILANCE

Future PV models lay stress on patient engagement as the key element of ADRs detection. Online apps and social media tracking enable patients to report on symptoms in real-time as an addition to the old methods of reporting. Patient education and awareness also enable patients to identify and communicate ADRs to improve drug safety surveillance.

The multimodal technologies incorporated into the Electronic Medical Records system need to be integrated, as they can help enhance both performance and user interfaces.

8.6 MULTIMODEL TECHNOLOGIES

Production into Electronic Medical Records system Multimodal technologies introduced into the Electronic Medical Records system should be integrated because they can assist in improving performance and user interfaces.

Pharmacovigilance as a component of diabetes management is likely to evolve into an AI, wearables, big data, and patient engagement-centered system in the future. The digital pharmacovigilance platforms can:

- Predict ADRs before they occur.
- Personalize treatment regimens.

- Enable regulatory bodies to implement timely safety interventions. predictive, and patient-centered discipline, ensuring safer diabetes management globally^{52,59}.

These innovations aim to transform pharmacovigilance from a reactive to a preventive,

Key Digital Innovations in Pharmacovigilance

Technology	Function / Application	Advantages	Current Challenges	References
Artificial Intelligence / ML	ADR prediction, signal detection	Fast data analysis, early detection	Data quality, algorithm transparency	37,53,59
Big Data & RWE	Integrating real-world evidence	Identifies long-term ADRs	Privacy and interoperability issues	56,60
Blockchain	Secure data sharing	Transparency, tamper-proof reporting	Technical complexity	57,58
Wearable Devices	Continuous glucose & safety monitoring	Real-time ADR detection	Cost, patient compliance	54,55
Mobile Apps / e-Reporting	Patient self-reporting of ADRs	Improves engagement, speeds reporting	Validation and training needed	59

9. DISCUSSION

Pharmacovigilance data indicate that hypoglycemia, gastrointestinal intolerance, and weight gain are among the most frequently reported ADRs across multiple antidiabetic drug classes. Post-marketing surveillance and real-world data have highlighted rare but serious ADRs, including lactic acidosis, pancreatitis, and euglycemic diabetic ketoacidosis, which require early detection and intervention^{35,51}. ADR patterns vary according to patient age, comorbidities, polypharmacy, and regional reporting practices, emphasizing the need for robust and standardized PV systems²⁷.

10. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Pharmacovigilance is important in the process of facilitating the safe and effective utility of antidiabetic drugs, limiting adverse drug reactions (ADRs), and risk-balancing therapeutic outcomes in patients with diabetes mellitus⁵⁰. This survey identifies the global and national pharmacovigilance systems, ADR trends of different antidiabetic pharmacological groups, and the new technology of digital monitoring and predictive analytics.

The evidence testifies to the fact that typical ADRs are hypoglycemia, gastrointestinal discomfort, weight gain, edema, hepatotoxicity, pancreatitis, and infrequent occurrence of euglycemic diabetic

ketoacidosis³². Such reactions differ between classes of drugs, comorbidities, polypharmacy and regional reporting. Although such international programs as WHO PIDM, VigiBase, EudraVigilance, or FAERS exist, as well as national projects, like PvPI in India, underreporting and partial fusion of data are still the issue of concern^{38,41,50}.

New technological materials such as artificial intelligence, wearable monitoring, blockchain, and patient-centered mobile applications offer new opportunities to predict real-time ADR and report⁴⁵. When incorporated into pharmacovigilance tools, these tools have the potential to convert the current reactive model of monitoring to a predictive model of monitoring.

RECOMMENDATION:

1. Enhance ADR reporting systems and professional training to curb the underreporting.
2. Real-time pharmacovigilance/wearable predictive monitoring with AI and wearable technologies.
3. Standardize ADR terminologies in the world to provide a standard reporting and data levels.
4. Foster involvement of patients in reporting of ADRs with health staff.

5. Technologically promote international regulatory cooperation to improve safety signals among others and prompted interventions.

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